

LEARNING A NEW LANGUAGE – TASKS INVOLVED

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Cite This Article: S. Gomathy, “Learning a New Language – Tasks Involved”, International Journal of Applied and Advanced Scientific Research, Volume 2, Issue 2, Page Number 8-9, 2017.

“Change is the end result of all true learning.” — Leo Buscaglia

Learning means change - a mental change which results in attitudinal change. Learning English as the second language will result in change of attitude. Unlimited languages are there for everyone to learn. India has more than 34 languages of spoken ones. English is the language brought to India before Independence by the British rulers. After Independence also, it has not left Indians as Nehru, Rajaji felt the need for it to be learnt, to make the future generation knowledgeable. As scientific facts and Technological inventions are available majorly in English, it has maintained its prestigious place. Learning English and becoming fluent is an ever tensioning matter for Indians. Though they are knowledgeable in English, the fluency is achieved only when they start speaking. English speaking skill is the prime skill the employers want in their employees. Today's world has opened the gate for international business on a massive scale and this has necessitated the knowledge and spoken fluency of English. How to learn English in an easier way? is the focus of the paper.

Key Words: Learning, Not Mother Tongue, English, Jobs, International Business & Spoken Fluency

Introduction:

English, a foreign language has become an inevitable part of our daily communication. We use English in our correspondence with companies, clients and for learning more about the business. English people have left India, but not English. It has become the interstate and intrastate communicative language in India. Even though there are many Indian languages and Hindi being the national language, English still rules our country. So, learning of English and trying to be fluent in English becomes mandatory for people who seek employment and for those who do business in a larger scale like export and import which includes interaction with different nationals.

How to Learn English in an Easier Way?

Spoken fluency can be achieved only by speaking. This may puzzle some. Unless we practice regularly any new skill cannot be acquired. Likewise, speaking in English can be achieved only by trying and speaking in English. For example when someone wants to learn cycling, he tries it. He tries to ride the cycle – he falls many times. Then by regular practice, he learns to ride managing his equilibrium. Learning to speak is also like that only. The knowledge must be tried with speaking in English and by committing mistake; the person knows how to avoid it. He learns to speak in simple language and slowly improves his word power also. As Samuel Butler says, “Don't learn to do, but learn in doing” By speaking English, English speaking skill can be enhanced.

Communicative Method of Learning:

This is one of the methods of learning new language - especially English. English teachers find this very much useful in making the students speak in English. It is a modern methodology. It includes various activity based tools. Role plays, Group discussions and public speaking on a given topic help the students to feel free in speaking in English. By repeated communication with speaking in English often, the basic barriers of communication like shyness, hesitation are all overcome. This method has proved itself worthy in developing fluency in English communication.

Aural Approach:

This method is a natural way of listening and thus learning to speak any language. This is how all of us have learnt our mother tongue. Every one of us have learnt our mother tongue by listening to our parents, neighbours who speak the same language. We listened and started to speak our mother tongue without any strain or stressful effort. The aural English teaching method is an approach best used for younger students, as it most closely relates to the way they've been used to learning language.

Creating English Speaking Environment:

In this method, the students and the teachers have inter and intra communication only in English. As the students listen and try to comprehend what is taught in English, they become good listeners and their understanding of English improves. This method works best for situations where the instructor does not speak the native language of the students they're instructing. It is also an ideal method for situations where there is a diverse set of students who don't share the same native language, all trying to learn English. This way, the barriers and constraints brought in by an inability to communicate natively can be dismissed, and a stronger focus on the language at hand can be made. When the students face English speaking environment, they are helped to listen and speak without hesitation.

Traditional Method of Translation:

This translative method of teaching language makes use of grammar, vocabulary, syntax for making the students learn. This minimizes the student interaction as it is a method of lecture and teacher instruction.

Though there are sessions of clarification, the students those who are really interested in learning a new language only show interest. It will be taught academically, as any other subject, best for students learning the English language because of an academic interest in it as a language, and not just an interest or need to know how to speak it.

Eclecticism:

This uses fitting the method to the learner, not the learner to the method. In recent days many colleges and universities have started conducting soft skills training to enhance the employability skills among the students. As more Multi National Companies have entered India for business deals, now all Indian students face a situation of, fluent spoken English becoming mandatory to get jobs in companies who pay them well. The employability depends on good and effective, fluent communication skills – especially in English. Soft skills training mainly focuses on spoken fluency, effective communication among the students. Now colleges have started allocating spoken English hours for training them in English communication. English language hours are separately allotted. To make the students confident in speaking in English the eclectic method is used. It is learner centered. How to be effective in communication? Is given as training. Persuasive communication, brief and prompt ways of communication is given. Joseph Priestley observes that the more elaborate our means of communication, the less we communicate. It necessitates word power to speak out well. Teaching the students to speak in English correctly and effectively is the task that is possible with soft skills incorporated training for achieving the purpose.

Watching Movies in the Target Language:

This helps to listen to the accent of the native speaker and thus enhances the listener's ability to understand. As listening is the first and foremost skill of communication it is gained in an effective way. In many colleges it is a practice of making the students watch English movies with scientific inventions and wild life discovery to make them feel more interested.

Making Friends with Other Language Speaking Students:

When a student is friendly with somebody who does not speak his mother tongue, he has to use English which is the connecting language. Interpersonal communication becomes possible only in English. Thus English speaking becomes mandatory and the speaker gains fluency as he starts speaking in it. His regular usage makes him comfortable and fluent in using it since his communication is with a person from other spoken medium and if the person is a native speaker of English, the learner is blessed with more chances of learning accuracy without strenuous effort. By listening to him and answering him the learner has an opportunity to listen and speak well in English.

SMART Goal Setting:

By setting a SMART goal of achieving English fluency will help the students gain fluency. Self commitment will make them try speaking in English. Continuous trial will result in achievement of the targeted language fluency. To achieve the target language fluency, reading books will help a lot. It is always found true that voracious readers are empowered with more vocabulary. All readers, including educated ones come across with many new words which the readers learn to use it in future. When they start using it, they learn to use it in context and become efficient at the usage of the learnt words. So setting small goals will help the learners more.

Conclusion:

English teaching learning methods are becoming student centered. Modern tools of Audio Visual aids, incorporating soft skills , Eclecticism , Aural method, Computer Aided Language Learning (with listening comprehension) are the latest ones used in teaching -learning English or any other new language which is not the native language of the learner. With modernization of the world with various technological advancements these are some methods which are found useful in new language learning and teaching. Task based language teaching with communicative language teaching methods are more useful when compared to others.

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